

CALCULATION OF HEAT REMOVAL FROM A PIPE BURIED IN THE SOIL

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An analytical solution is developed for steady-state heat transfer from a buried circular pipe to greenhouse soil, modeled using a point source (logarithmic singularity). The source location differs from the pipe center. An approximate heat transfer condition on the soil surface is introduced, with negligible error in practice. Explicit equations are provided for soil temperature distribution, surface temperature, total heat flux from the pipe, and surface heat flux density. This approach addresses sustainable heating using secondary energy resources.

Keywords: thermal power, heat flux density, circular isotherm, temperature distribution.

Introduction. The use of secondary energy resources is a cornerstone of sustainable development. One of the promising areas for the utilization of secondary energy resources is their use in the heating systems of agricultural greenhouses [1–3]. Soil temperature strongly affects seed germination, seeding emergence, root development, and plant growth [4, 5]. Therefore, the optimal temperature of the soil determines a high crop yield. Deviation from optimal thermal conditions results in heat or water loss, bacterial and fungal infections, and reduced soil productivity [6]. Therefore, a topical problem is the thermal calculation of the process of heat removal to the greenhouse soil for its heating, as well as monitoring the effects of various parameters on the temperature conditions of the soil [7, 8]. To solve this problem, it is necessary to develop a mathematical model that describes the process of heat removal to the soil, taking into account various parameters.

The analysis of heat transfer between a heat source and the surrounding soil is a complex problem that requires the consideration of many factors, such as ambient air parameters, soil properties, and design features of heat exchange devices [9, 10]. In particular, the influence of the following parameters on the thermal conditions has been actively studied: pipe length and diameter [11, 12], pipe (buried) depth, soil type [13, 14], pipe number [15, 16], and fluid velocity [14, 17, 18].

To better understand the thermal characteristics of widely used soil heat exchangers, numerous heat transfer models have been developed, which can be divided into analytical models [14, 15, 19, 20] and numerical models [21–26]. The limited applicability of existing models, their complexity, and their weak correlation with experimental data determine the relevance of the issue for calculating the thermal field of the soil.

This study aimed to propose a calculation method for an analytical solution to the problem of heat removal from a circular pipe buried in the soil. The usual way to calculate the thermal field of the soil is based on numerical modeling within the framework of grid methods. The scientific novelty of this work is that an approximate analytical solution is developed, which can be useful when verifying the results of such models. The study is based on a normalized mathematical formulation, which provides explicit equations for the temperature distribution inside the soil and on its surface, for the total heat flux removed from the pipe, and for the distribution of the heat flux density on the soil surface. The feature of this work is to estimate the accuracy of the approximations introduced for the formulated problem.

Problem formulation. We consider steady-state heat removal from a circular pipe of unlimited length located under the horizontal surface of the soil (fig. 1). By R denotes a radius of the pipe, having surface temperature t_w , and by b^* ($b^* > R$) denotes the depth of the buried pipe (the distance from the surface of the soil to the pipe axis). The body of the soil is homogeneous and occupies a half-space; the thermal conductivity coefficient of the soil λ is constant. The heat transfer to air with the coefficient α is set on the surface of the soil. The soil temperature is limited at a distance from the pipe, so this temperature approaches the air temperature t_f ($t_f < t_w$). It is necessary to determine the thermal power Q of the removal of heat from the pipe and the temperature field of the soil, particularly the temperature on its surface t_0 , and the distribution of the heat flux density on the soil surface q_0 .

Fig. 1. Calculation scheme

The problem is plane. Instead of temperature t , we consider the excessive temperature $\vartheta = t - t_f$, accordingly denoting $\vartheta_w = t_w - t_f$.

Suppose that the heat flux lines approach the soil surface almost normally. The effect of the thermal resistance of the soil surface can be considered equivalent to the thermal resistance of the soil layer with a thickness of $\sigma^* = \lambda / \alpha$. This is true if the following condition is met:

$$\sigma^* \ll \sqrt{(b^*)^2 - R^2}.$$

Therefore, instead of the initial area, we consider an area with an additional layer with a thickness σ^* placed on top of the initial surface of the soil, where the upper boundary has a temperature equal to the temperature of the air. Therefore, such a ‘normalized’ formulation differs in the pipe depth $b = b^* + \sigma^*$ with the boundary condition (1) on the soil surface, considering that the origin (x, y) lies on the ‘normalized’ soil surface above the center of the pipe, so the y axis is directed vertically upward, and the x axis is horizontal (along the ‘normalized’ surface of the soil). In this case, the center of the pipe is located at $x_c = 0$, $y_c = -b$:

$$\vartheta|_{y=0} = 0. \tag{1}$$

Thus, in this ‘normalized’ mathematical formulation, the required function $\vartheta(x, y)$ must satisfy the equation of steady-state thermal conductivity $\nabla^2 \vartheta = 0$ in the area under consideration $(x^2 + (y+b)^2 > R^2) \cap (y < 0)$ with boundary condition (1) and (2):

$$\vartheta|_{x^2+(y+b)^2=R^2} = \vartheta_w. \tag{2}$$

Solution of the equations. The solution to the problem with a similar mathematical formulation was given in the works of [27, 28] in the form:

$$\vartheta(x, y) = \frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + (y-h)^2}{x^2 + (y+h)^2}}. \tag{3}$$

where Q is the thermal power removed from the pipe; and where $h = b$ is taken. The following equation links Q and ϑ_w :

$$Q = \frac{2\pi\lambda \vartheta_w}{\ln(2h/R)}.$$

This solution is approximate (discussed in more detail in Subsection Parameter control), although the results have a negligible error at $R \ll h$.

For the general case, an exact solution of the problem is preferable. This solution comes from (3) for two singularities placed in the plane (x, y) : a heat source at the point $x = 0, y = -h$ and a sink at the point $x = 0, y = h$; these singularities have the same intensity Q (not yet specified). Since the isotherms of this temperature field are circular (see Subsection Solution of the equations), the line $y = 0$ with temperature $\vartheta = 0$ is considered a special case of a circle. Naturally, the circles are nonconcentric, and in the half-plane $y < 0$, with an increase in the radius of the circular isotherms, their centers shift downward from the source (fig. 2, at $h = 1$). Therefore, the following condition is observed for an isotherm corresponding to the pipe surface:

$$b - R < h < b. \tag{3a}$$

Fig. 2. Isotherms of the temperature field

The heat flux lines are also arcs of circles between these singularities (fig. 3). It is clear that only part of the field at $y < 0$ (more precisely, at $y < -\sigma^*$) has a physical meaning.

Fig. 3. Flow net

Solution of the equations. Analytical solutions to plane boundary value problems for physical fields are often based on the placement of singularities in the area under consideration [29]. Evidently, the simplest type of singularity is the source at the origin, described for the coordinates (u, v) by the function:

$$\vartheta(u, v) = -\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln r, \text{ where } r = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}. \quad (4)$$

Function (4) can be considered as given on the entire plane (u, v) , except for the point $u = v = 0$. Obviously, this is a mathematical abstraction, for example, owing to the nonphysicality of infinitely negative temperature values ϑ at large r , and infinitely large values at small r .

Note that (4) is harmonic, i.e., it meets the equation of thermal conductivity $\nabla^2 \vartheta = 0$ and describes some conditional temperature fields. The isotherms of the temperature field are concentric circles with $r = \text{const}$, and the heat flux lines are rectilinear rays (coming from the origin), as shown in fig. 4. In particular, a practical solution can be found in any region between two isotherms to address the problem of thermal conductivity of a circular wall.

Fig. 4. Temperature chart

An effective way to determine analytical solutions is to use complex variables and functions. If $w = u + iv$, then (4) can be written as:

$$\vartheta = -\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln|w|. \quad (5)$$

If $z = x + iy$, then the temperature field can be calculated via (3) according to [27, 28] as follows:

$$\vartheta = \frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln \left| \frac{z - ih}{z + ih} \right|. \quad (6)$$

As noted above, this is the sum of the source $-\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln|z + ih|$ at the point $z = -ih$ and the sink $\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln|z - ih|$ at the point $z = ih$. However, function (5) actually describes the field of the source at the origin $w = 0$ and the sink at the point at infinity $w = \infty$. The analytical function $w = \frac{z + ih}{z - ih}$ performs a conformal mapping between the planes of variables z and w , where the points $w = 0$ and $w = \infty$ correspond to the points $z = -ih$ and $z = ih$, respectively. This function is fractionally linear; that is, with this mapping, the circles are mutually transformed into circles [28]. This proves that, in fact, in the z plane the isotherms will also be circular, and the heat flux lines will be arcs of circles ($\vartheta(z) = \vartheta(w(z))$).

Corrected equations. Thus, the temperature field $\vartheta(x, y)$, corresponding to the formulation presented in Section Problem formulation, must have the form of (3), where h is the required parameter. If p is an argument of the logarithm in (3), then:

$$p = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + (y - h)^2}{x^2 + (y + h)^2}}. \quad (7)$$

Find p at the upper point D and the lower point A of the pipe contour $p_D = \left| \frac{y_D - h}{y_D + h} \right|$ and $p_A = \left| \frac{y_A - h}{y_A + h} \right|$ respectively, taking into account that $x = 0$ and $y_D = -(b - R)$, $y_A = -(b + R)$.

Since the surface of the pipe is an isotherm, so $p_D = p_A$, and with (3a) $\frac{b - R + h}{-b + R + h} = \frac{b + R + h}{b + R - h}$, then $b^2 - (h - R)^2 = (h + R)^2 - b^2$ or:

$$h^2 = b^2 - R^2. \quad (8)$$

Total thermal power. In order to use (3), it is necessary to determine Q . By p_0 denotes p on the contour of the pipe:

$$\begin{aligned} p_0 = p_D &= \frac{h + b - R}{h - b + R} = \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - R^2} + b - R}{\sqrt{b^2 - R^2} - b + R} = \frac{(\sqrt{b^2 - R^2} + b - R)^2}{b^2 - R^2 - (b - R)^2} = \\ &= \frac{b^2 - R^2 + b^2 - 2bR + R^2 + 2\sqrt{b^2 - R^2}(b - R)}{b^2 - R^2 - b^2 + 2bR - R^2} = \frac{2b(b - R) + 2\sqrt{b^2 - R^2}(b - R)}{2b(b - R)}, \end{aligned}$$

so:

$$p_0 = \frac{b}{R} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{b}{R}\right)^2 - 1}. \quad (9)$$

With boundary condition (2), substituting $\vartheta = \vartheta_w$ and $p = p_0$ in (3), we obtain:

$$Q = \frac{2\pi\lambda}{\ln p_0} \vartheta_w. \quad (10)$$

Heat flux on the soil surface. To consider the distribution of the heat flux input from below, we need to calculate the vertical component of the heat flux density. Returning to (6) in terms of identity from [30] and $\vartheta = \operatorname{Re}\left(\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln \frac{z-ih}{z+ih}\right)$:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{Q}{2\pi\lambda} \ln \frac{z-ih}{z+ih} \right) = \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y}. \quad (11)$$

We obtain the following:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\ln \frac{z-ih}{z+ih} \right) = \frac{z+ih}{z-ih} \cdot \frac{(z+ih) - (z-ih)}{(z+ih)^2} = \frac{2ih}{z^2 + h^2}. \quad (12)$$

The problem formulation includes finding the distribution $q_0(x)$ of the heat flux density on the soil surface. As noted above, the ‘practical’ surface of the soil in the ‘normalized’ formulation corresponds to the line $y = -\sigma^*$. However, the ‘normalized’ formulation in Section Problem formulation is based on the proximity of these distributions on the lines $y = -\sigma^*$ and $y = 0$. Therefore, it is permissible to take $q_0(x)$ as the distribution $q_0(x) = q_y(x, y)|_{y=0}$ on the ‘normalized’ soil surface. From (11) and (12) it is clear that at $y = 0$ (i.e., $z = x$) $\partial \vartheta / \partial x = 0$ and $q_x = 0$, as according to (1). And:

$$q_0(x) = -\lambda \left. \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = \frac{Q}{\pi} \frac{h}{x^2 + h^2}. \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) can be represented in a dimensionless form as the dependence of the dimensionless intensity of heat removal $\pi q_0 h / Q$ on the dimensionless coordinate x / h :

$$\frac{q_0 h}{Q} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{1}{1 + (x/h)^2}. \quad (14)$$

In fig. 5 this dependence is shown as a single curve for all the input parameters (see also the velocity curve along the upper boundary in fig. 3). It is evident from the curve that the heat flux density is at a maximum directly above the pipe and decreases, in particular, by 2 times at a distance h (pipe depth).

Since the heat fluxes on the surface are determined, on the basis of Newton's relation for heat transfer $q_0(x) = \alpha(t_0(x) - t_f)$, we can find the temperature distribution $t_0(x)$ of the initial surface of the soil:

$$t_0(x) = t_f + q_0(x) / \alpha. \quad (15)$$

Fig. 5. Heat flux density vs. pipe depth

Parameter control.

a) Next, we estimate the difference between b and h . As noted above, (3) corresponds to the modeling of the temperature field of the pipe by the field from the source located at the point $x = 0$, $y = -h$, i.e., with an upward shift from the center of the pipe with coordinates $x = 0$, $y = -b$. As indicated in Section Solution of the equations, $h = b$ [27,28], and to calculate Q via (10), instead of the exact solution for p_0 using (9), we take:

$$p_0 = \frac{2h}{R}. \quad (16)$$

Calculating this shift $\delta = b - h$ via (8) shows that at a sufficiently large relative depth of the pipe this simplification is admissible and results in a small error. Therefore, at $b/R \geq 10$ (five pipe diameters), the δ -value will be less than 5% of the radius R and less than 0.5% of the depth b ; even at $b/R = 5$, δ will be 10 and 2%, respectively. The error in calculating p_0 via (16) for these values of b/R will be even less than 1%. These errors can be considered acceptable. But at a small depth, especially at $b/R < 4$, the errors exceed 12 and 3%, so the simplifications taken are undesirable.

b) Furthermore, we check that the pipe contour is an isotherm. As mentioned above, isotherms of the temperature field via (3) have the shape of circles, in particular, an isotherm with $\vartheta = \vartheta_w$, corresponding to the boundary of the pipe. The temperatures at the upper point D ($x = 0$, $y = -b + R$) and lower point A ($x = 0$, $y = -b - R$) of the contour are equal in construction, since $p_D = p_A = p_0$. For verification, via (7), we find p at the 'right' point B of the contour, where $x = R$, $y = -b$:

$$p_B = \sqrt{\frac{x^2 + (y-h)^2}{x^2 + (y+h)^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{R^2 + (b+h)^2}{R^2 + (b-h)^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{R^2 + b^2 + 2bh + h^2}{R^2 + b^2 - 2bh + h^2}}.$$

Substituting (8) yields:

$$p_B = \sqrt{\frac{R^2 + b^2 + 2bh + b^2 - R^2}{R^2 + b^2 - 2bh + b^2 - R^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{2b(b+h)}{2b(b-h)}} = \sqrt{\frac{(b+h)(b+h)}{(b-h)(b+h)}} = \frac{b+h}{\sqrt{b^2 - b^2 + R^2}},$$

and via (9), we get $p_B = \frac{b + \sqrt{b^2 - R^2}}{R} = p_0$.

Therefore, at this point of the circle, the parameter p and, correspondingly, the temperature are equal in accordance with (3) to the values at points D and A . This confirms that this circle is an isotherm.

Algorithm for solving the problem. Thus, in the initial formulation, the following parameters are set: pipe radius R , pipe depth b^* , surface temperature t_w , and the thermal conductivity coefficient of the soil λ . On the surface of the soil the heat transfer coefficient α at the air temperature t_f is set. The total thermal power Q , the distribution of the heat flux density q_0 , and the temperature on the soil surface t_0 must be determined.

The proposed solution consists of calculating the following values: the temperature difference $\vartheta_w = t_w - t_f$, the ‘normalized’ pipe depth $b = b^* + \sigma^*$ (where $\sigma^* = \lambda / \alpha$), the parameter p_0 via (9), and the thermal power Q using (10). After finding the parameter h via (8), it is possible to determine the distribution $q_0(x)$ using (13) or (14), as well as $t_0(x)$ via (15).

If temperatures at other points in the soil or other characteristics are needed, (3) can be used, taking into account that $\vartheta = t - t_f$, and $y = -\sigma^*$ on the ‘practical’ soil surface, so that at the soil points $y < \sigma^*$.

Estimated accuracy of heat transfer. The analytical solution to the problem is exact for the ‘normalized’ formulation presented in Section Problem formulation, but this formulation contains an approximation of substituting the heat transfer condition with a fictitious layer of soil with a thickness σ^* . The nature of the errors introduced by this substitution requires a close estimation.

a) Variable heat transfer coefficient $\tilde{\alpha}(x)$. The real boundary of the soil in the formulation (Section Problem formulation) corresponds to the line $y = -\sigma^*$, where for the initial formulation, the Newton–Richman heat transfer condition must be met in the form $\frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = -\frac{\alpha}{\lambda} \vartheta$, where $\alpha = \text{const}$ is the given heat transfer coefficient. This condition is not strictly met in the case of the proposed solution to the problem. However, we can assume that this condition works for some variable coefficient $\tilde{\alpha}(x)$:

$$\frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial y} = -\frac{\tilde{\alpha}(x)}{\lambda} \vartheta \text{ at } y = -\sigma^*. \quad (17)$$

By comparing $\tilde{\alpha}$ and α , we can estimate the accuracy of the substitution performed.

b) Dimensionless variables. The error clearly depends on the relative thickness σ^*/h of the fictitious layer introduced. This thickness is directly related to the conditional Bio number of the problem ($\text{Bi} = \frac{\alpha \cdot h}{\lambda}$); therefore, $\frac{\sigma^*}{h} = \frac{1}{\text{Bi}}$. Accordingly, the following calculations are performed in the dimensionless form by introducing the dimensionless variables $X = x/h$, $Y = y/h$, and $\Theta = \vartheta \cdot \lambda / Q$. Then by (3):

$$\Theta = \frac{1}{4\pi} \ln \frac{X^2 + (1-Y)^2}{X^2 + (1+Y)^2}. \quad (18)$$

and differentiation of (3) or (18), we get:

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{X^2 + 1 - Y^2}{(X^2 + 1 - Y^2)^2 + 4X^2Y^2}. \quad (19)$$

If $Bi = \frac{\tilde{\alpha} \cdot h}{\lambda}$, then from (17) we obtain that:

$$\frac{1}{Bi} = - \left. \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} \right|_{Y=-\frac{1}{Bi}} \quad (20)$$

c) Estimation of $\tilde{\alpha}$ at $x = 0$. First, we analyze the accuracy of α at the point of the soil surface directly above the pipe, i.e., at $X = 0, Y = -1/Bi$. When $X = 0$, from (19), we get $\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{1-Y^2}$, and from (18), taking into account the known expansion in a series $\ln \frac{1-\phi}{1+\phi} = -2(\phi + \frac{\phi^3}{3} + \frac{\phi^5}{5} + \dots)$, we obtain $\Theta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \ln \frac{1-Y}{1+Y} = -\frac{Y}{\pi} (1 + \frac{Y^2}{3} + \frac{Y^4}{5} + \dots)$. Then at $X = 0$, substituting in (20), we get the following:

$$\frac{1}{Bi} = - \left. \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} \right|_{Y=-\frac{1}{Bi}} = -Y (1 + \frac{Y^2}{3} + \frac{Y^4}{5} + \dots) (1-Y^2) \Big|_{Y=-\frac{1}{Bi}} = \frac{1}{Bi} \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{Bi} \right)^2 + O\left(\frac{1}{Bi^4} \right) \right].$$

This value is compared with the heat transfer given at this point via (21):

$$\frac{\alpha}{\tilde{\alpha}} = \frac{Bi}{Bi} \Big|_{Y=-\frac{1}{Bi}} = 1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{Bi} \right)^2 + O\left(\frac{1}{Bi^4} \right). \quad (21)$$

Therefore, the relative error in the heat transfer rate at this point for a small $1/Bi$ is approximately $\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{Bi} \right)^2$. Moreover, calculations show (see the paragraph below) that for other points of the boundary the error (in absolute value) is even lower. Thus, this is a general estimation of the accuracy for α along the entire boundary.

d) As an example, suppose that $\lambda = 0.5 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, $\alpha = 10 \text{ W/(m}^2\cdot\text{K)}$, the depth of the pipe $b^* = 0.5 \text{ m}$ with diameter $2R = 0.2 \text{ m}$. Additionally, $\sigma^* = 0.05 \text{ m}$, $b = 0.55 \text{ m}$, $h = 0.54$, $Bi = 10.8$, and the relative error $\frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{1}{Bi} \right)^2 = 0.0057$. Calculations of the temperature field according to (3) and the developed calculation algorithm are performed for heat transfer with a value-added height above the pipe compared to the initial set of a half percent. This error can be considered to be insignificant for most practical problems. If α or b^* increases and λ or R decreases, then this error will be even smaller.

e) Calculation of the distribution $\tilde{\alpha}(x)$ along the boundary of the soil. The results of the calculations using (22), (18), and (19) show that the excess of $\tilde{\alpha}$ over the initial value α is maximized exactly at point $X = 0$ (over the pipe), and this excess fully corresponds to (21). With distance from this point, the error decreases and reaches zero at X slightly more than half. This point is the same for all Bi numbers. Furthermore, the $\tilde{\alpha}$ -value is undersized, although even the maximum decrease (in absolute value) is less than the maximum increase.

Figure 6 shows the distribution curves $\tilde{\alpha}(x)/\alpha$ for different Bi numbers. After reaching a minimum, the ratio $\tilde{\alpha}(x)/\alpha$ tends to zero with increasing x (see the next paragraph). Specifically, the error of the calculated temperatures and the heat fluxes decreases with an increasing x , not only because these values approach zero. Additionally, the accuracy of accounting $\tilde{\alpha}$ also increases, albeit relatively slowly. The average distribution $\tilde{\alpha}(x)$ approximately corresponds to the initial α -value (see also paragraph below).

Fig. 6. Distribution $\tilde{\alpha}(x)/\alpha$

f) Behavior of $\tilde{\alpha}$ at a distance. From Fig. 6 it is not seen that the curves on the right approach zero. This fact is clear from the calculations for $X \geq 10$, so we obtain this analytically.

We next show that with increasing x , the value of $\tilde{\alpha}(x)/\alpha$ tends to zero, i.e.:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tilde{\alpha}}{\alpha} = \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\overline{\text{Bi}}}{\text{Bi}} = 1.$$

By (20), we get the following:

$$\frac{\overline{\text{Bi}}}{\text{Bi}} = - \frac{1}{\text{Bi}} \frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} \Bigg|_{Y = \frac{1}{\text{Bi}}} \quad (22)$$

From (18):

$$\Theta = \frac{1}{4\pi} \ln \frac{X^2 + (1-Y)^2}{X^2 + (1+Y)^2} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \ln \frac{X^2 + (1+Y)^2 + (1-Y)^2 - (1+Y)^2}{X^2 + (1+Y)^2} =$$

$$= \frac{1}{4\pi} \ln\left(1 + \frac{(1-Y+1+Y)(1-Y-1-Y)}{X^2 + (1+Y)^2}\right) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \ln\left(1 - \frac{2 \cdot 2Y}{X^2 + (1+Y)^2}\right),$$

therefore, at $X \rightarrow \infty$, we have:

$$\Theta \sim -\frac{1}{4\pi} \cdot \frac{4Y}{X^2} = -\frac{Y}{\pi X^2}. \quad (23)$$

Using (19):

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{X^2 + 1 - Y^2}{(X^2 + 1 - Y^2)^2 + 4X^2Y^2} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{1}{(X^2 + 1 - Y^2) + \frac{4X^2Y^2}{X^2 + 1 - Y^2}},$$

and at $X \rightarrow \infty$, we get:

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y} \sim -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{1}{X^2}. \quad (24)$$

Substituting (23) and (24) into (22) yields:

$$\lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\overline{\text{Bi}}}{\text{Bi}} = -\frac{1}{\text{Bi}} \cdot \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial Y}}{\Theta} = -\frac{1}{\text{Bi}} \cdot \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\frac{1}{\pi X^2}}{\frac{Y}{\pi X^2}} = -\frac{1}{\text{Bi}} \cdot \frac{1}{Y},$$

and, taking into account that on the line of the soil surface $Y = -1/\text{Bi}$, we obtain the following:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tilde{\alpha}}{\alpha} = \lim_{X \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\overline{\text{Bi}}}{\text{Bi}} = 1.$$

g) About the variability of the distribution $\tilde{\alpha}$. Certainly, under real conditions, heat transfer on the soil surface is realized either by free convection (in a greenhouse, etc.), or by a free-convective mechanism (wind, blowing, etc.). In the case of free convection, the heat transfer coefficient directly depends on the temperature difference, so the ‘canonical’ condition $\alpha = \text{const}$ is an idealization or an approximate simplification of the real situation. Therefore, the variability of the heat transfer coefficient, when it slightly increases in the area of the main heat fluxes of the soil above the pipe and decreases together with the temperature, changes the solution toward the real situation (of course, insignificantly).

Conclusions. This paper proposes the use of recovered system thermal loss to heat the soil of agricultural greenhouses, where maintaining an optimal temperature regime is extremely important for the yield of crops. Numerical mathematical models are complex because many factors influence the temperature distribution process in the soil. The authors present an analytical solution to the problem of heat removal to the soil surface from a buried pipe. The problem is one-dimensional and is considered under steady-state conditions. The temperature field is modeled by a distribution from a point source (logarithmic singularity of the harmonic function). It has been proven that the isotherms of the temperature field are circular. The location of the heat source in the exact formulation does not coincide with the center of the pipe. The condition of heat transfer on the soil surface is substituted by the approximate condition.

An estimation of the accuracy of such a substitution is given; it is shown that in practical problems, even with sufficiently large relative depths of the pipe, such a simplification is permissible and results in a small error. Explicit equations are presented for the temperature distribution in the soil and on its surface, for the total heat flux removed from the pipe, and for the distribution of the heat flux density on the surface of the soil. The calculation algorithm has been described for solving the problem of steady-state heat removal from a circular pipe buried in a soil body at a certain depth.

In the future, on the basis of the developed calculation method, the influence of the length and shape of the pipe, as well as the number of pipes on the temperature field of the soil during heat removal, should be studied.

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РАСЧЁТ ТЕПЛОТВОДА ОТ ТРУБЫ В ГРУНТЕ

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Разработано аналитическое решение задачи отвода тепла в почву теплицы от заглубленной в нее круглой трубы. Задача рассматривается в плоской постановке в стационарных условиях. Температурное поле моделируется распределением от точечного источника (логарифмическая особенность). Местоположение источника в случае точной постановки не совпадает с центром трубы. Условие теплопередачи на поверхности почвы заменяется приближенным с незначительной погрешностью на практике. Приведены явные уравнения для распределения температуры внутри почвы и на ее поверхности, для полного теплового потока, отводимого от трубы, и для распределения плотности теплового потока на поверхности почвы.

Ключевые слова: тепловая мощность, плотность теплового потока, круговая изотерма, распределение температуры.

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